

Temperature dependencies of dielectric properties in $\text{Na}_{1-x}\text{K}_x\text{TaO}_3$ system

Vijendra Lingwal, ¹A S Kandari and ²N S Panwar

*Pt. L.M.S. Govt. PG College Rishikesh, Dehradun-249201, Uttarakhand

¹Govt. PG College New Tehri, Uttarakhand

²University Science Instrumentation Centre, HNB Garhwal University, Srinagar (Garhwal)- 246174, Uttarakhand

E-mail : lingwalv@yahoo.co.in

Mobile No. : 9639302438

Pellet samples of mixed sodium-potassium tantalate ($\text{Na}_{1-x}\text{K}_x\text{TaO}_3$), for compositions $x = 0, 0.2$ and 0.5 were prepared by solid-state reaction method. The calcined mixture was pressed at 0.02 MPa and sintered in a closed furnace to form 6 mm diameter pellets. Temperature variation of dielectric constant and loss tangent of the prepared samples has been studied in the frequency range from 10 KHz to 1 MHz. Dielectric anomalies have been observed near the transition temperatures of the samples. Dielectric constant and loss tangent peak heights were observed decreasing with increasing frequency, for all the compositions, which show relaxational behavior of the material.

Keywords: Ferroelectrics, perovskite, dielectric constant, loss tangent, sintering.